

Widdringtonia wallichii Clanwilliam Cedar

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Group: Gymnosperm

Size: 15 meters.

Distribution:

Narrowly confined to the Cederberg, in the Western Cape.

Importance:

The Clanwilliam cedar, an iconic conifer of the Cederberg, is critically endangered. Its assembled genome will serve as a reference for mapping short-read sequences from trees of different ages and locations, allowing us to measure genetic diversity across space and time. These genetic insights will help guide seed-collection strategies and maximise genetic diversity in restoration efforts in the Cederberg.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 406.93 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 18.79 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 9.26 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 96.2% [Single: 92.9%, Duplicated: 3.3%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 325 649.65 kilobases

Contig number: 1871

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